

Varieties chosen as parents to constitute the gene pool.

Compatible reaction with the isolate	Varietal group	Incompatible reaction with the isolate	Varietal group
Azucena	6	62667	6
Arias	6	Araguaia	6
B2997C-TB-60-3-3	1	Diwani	1
CT6510-24-1-2	1	IR58662-04	6
IR53236-280	1	IR60080-46A	6
IR55419-04	1	IR63380-08	6
IR55435-05	1	IRAT 104	6
IRAT 169 F10/6	1	IRAT 212	6
Lubang red	1	IRAT 216	6
Palawan	6	Ketan Menah	6
Speaker	6	P5589-1-1-3P	6
Vandana	1	MedNoi	6

table). Twelve of them were susceptible to the chosen isolate and 12 were resistant.

The gene pool was created through three rounds of hybridization (see figure). To preserve the different cytoplasms, the hybridization scheme was circular. In the 1994 wet season (WS), each susceptible parent was crossed with a resistant one. The resulting F₁ hybrids were all expected to be resistant, since resistance attributable to a major gene is generally dominant. The

second round of crosses, done in 1995 DS, involved intermating between F₁s. The resulting double hybrids were segregating for the resistance/susceptibility to the isolate. Only the double recessive plants were transplanted in the hybridization block for the third round of crosses in the 1995 WS. The gene pool was then built with equal representation of the resulting hybrids.

The development of the GPIR-22 took 2 yr. Its improvement through recurrent selection has already started.

14 mo. After incubation, the percentages of infested seeds and weight loss ranged, respectively, from 10.5 to 61.5% and 5.5 to 26.1%. In addition, AGM-infested seeds were separated by genotype and subjected to the emergence evaluation in a screenhouse (Table 1).

Seeds were planted in plastic trays (50 × 42 × 8 cm), containing homogenized soil, in a completely randomized design with three replications of 20 seeds each, in a two-factor arrangement with five levels of infestation and nine genotypes. Emergence performance was evaluated 15 d later by counting the emerged seedlings and expressing the results in percentage for statistical analysis.

Both factors, genotype and level of infestation, had significant effects on seedling emergence but no interaction was observed between the factors. The majority of the genotypes showed a linear type response, with a consistent negative trend in emergence response to increased infestation levels. Only two genotypes, CNA 7451 and CNA 7890, demonstrated a quadratic effect. The regression equations calculated for each genotype are presented in Table 2.

By the end of the test period, around 1.8% of the emerged seedlings had died and 7.5% showed reduced growth. Significant differences were observed among genotypes subjected to the same level of infestation, and cultivars Guarani and IAC47 had the highest emergence rates. ■

Pest resistance—insects

Intensity of the attack of *Sitotroga cerealella* (Olivier) in rice genotypes and its effect on seedling emergence

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Angoumois grain moth (AGM), *Sitotroga cerealella* (Olivier), a storage grain pest, is responsible for great damage on seeds, causing weight loss, reduced nutrient content, and loss of viability. This study determined the correlation between levels of AGM storage infestation and seed performance of different rice genotypes.

The effect of AGM attack, which is related to the intensity of infestation,

was evaluated in nine genotypes randomly drawn from a total of 45 genotypes naturally infested in a field trial. Approximately 400 g of each genotype was placed in plastic boxes (16 × 12 × 6 cm) and incubated in the laboratory for

Table 1. Influence of grain moth *Sitotroga cerealella* (Olivier) level of infestation on seedling emergence of different rice genotypes. Santo Antônio de Goiás, Brazil. 1995.

Genotype	Level of infestation			
	00		80	
	Emergence(%)	SE	Emergence(%)	SE
CNA7645	41.7	11.5	8.3	5.8
CNA7690	70.0	5.0	18.3	5.8
Guarani	78.3	5.8	26.7	5.8
CNA7451	61.7	12.6	15.0	5.0
CNA7864	76.7	7.6	15.0	5.0
CNA7890	63.3	10.4	30.3	18.6
IAC1343	63.3	7.6	11.7	7.6
CIAT20	73.3	10.4	13.7	12.0
IAC47	81.7	7.6	15.0	8.0

Table 2. Regression equations calculated for each genotype considering seedling emergence as dependent variable of intensity of AGM attack. Santo Antônio de Goiás, Brazil. 1995

Genotype	Regression equation	R ^{2a}
CNA7645	Y ₁ = 45.000 - 0.458x	0.945**
CNA7690	Y ₂ = 64.333 - 0.625x	0.948**
Guarani	Y ₃ = 78.000 - 0.708x	0.932**
CNA7451	Y ₄ = 62.048 - 1.155x + 0.007x ²	0.993**
CNA7864	Y ₅ = 73.333 - 0.708x	0.968**
CNA7890	Y ₆ = 62.790 - 1.074x + 0.008x ²	0.935*
IAC1343	Y ₇ = 60.000 - 0.583x	0.897
CIAT20	Y ₈ = 71.267 - 0.780x	0.976**
IAC47	Y ₉ = 81.333 - 0.817x	0.995**

^a***=significant at .01 level of probability, *= significant at .05 level of probability.